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**“Living Heritage
and Sustainable Tourism”**

(supposed to take place)

April 6-8, 2020

Mendrisio, Switzerland

Edited by

**Lorenzo Cantoni, Silvia De Ascaniis,
& Karin Elgin-Nijhuis**

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**Heritage, Tourism and Hospitality
International Conference
HTHIC2020 – “Preceedings”
Mendrisio, Switzerland**

Foreword

The 4th edition of the *Heritage, Tourism and Hospitality, International Conference* was supposed to take place on April 6-8, 2020 in Mendrisio, Switzerland. Mendrisio was selected as a fascinating example of ‘living’ tangible and intangible heritage, because of its *Processioni della Settimana Santa* (Processions of the Holy Week) and the ‘transparencies’, which are translucent paintings mounted on wooden frames and illuminated from within. The transparencies are exposed on the city walls during the Processions, while they are kept in the Mendrisio Illuminated Paintings Museum during the year. The Processions are a unique event organized every year during the week preceding Easter; they have been inscribed on the UNESCO Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity in 2019¹.

The Conference was supposed to bring together professionals in the heritage and tourism fields, international scholars, and the local community, to study the relationships between living heritage and sustainable tourism, and all related issues – challenges and opportunities. It was also supposed to be a joyful celebration of the important recognition by UNESCO. All the involved players, the two organizing entities – Elgin & Co and USI-Università della Svizzera italiana –, the local stakeholders – Municipality of Mendrisio, Organizzazione Turistica Regionale Mendrisiotto e Basso Ceresio, and The Historical Processions Foundation – as well as many other organizations were fully prepared to launch and run a memorable Conference.

But COVID-19 has come on stage and changed everything.

Thus, the story had to continue within a very different frame and following a different narrative. We believe that this different, unexpected

¹ See the official page on the UNESCO website dedicated to Intangible Cultural Heritage: <https://ich.unesco.org/en/RL/holy-week-processions-in-mendrisio-01460>.

narrative, can shed some light in the challenging and sometimes scary times we are all living in; and maybe even this situation offers opportunities.

This is the reason why we decided to publish the text you are reading. They are the result of the shared effort of authors who submitted their work to the Conference, and the chairs, who coordinated the process and ensured its consistency. They aim at being an instrument for promoting knowledge and fostering reflection about the relationship between Heritage, Tourism and Hospitality, in an even more intense and focused way during the time of Coronavirus. Since the 4th edition of HTHIC could not take place in April 2020, the documents that you are about to read are not PRO-ceedings, but rather PRE-ceedings... They represent, in fact, the wish for the Conference to be however a tool to get better PRE-pared for the time when the pandemic will be over and the heritage, tourism and hospitality fields will face new challenges and opportunities.

The papers submitted to the Conference have been grouped according to four themes, which help, from different perspectives, to answer the leading question of the conference: *how can tourism destinations succeed in attracting tourists while simultaneously engaging all stakeholders in the conservation of natural and cultural heritage?*

While introducing this “Preceedings” volume, we would like to share some reflections on issues that the current situation is bringing to the field of heritage, tourism and hospitality.

According to UNWTO, “this pandemic affects every level of society and we stand by those affected in these times. The impact of the pandemic on already slowing economies has made tourism particularly vulnerable, becoming the hardest hit sector so far. With 80% of the sector made up of small and medium-sized enterprises, millions of livelihoods in the world are left vulnerable²”. Since traveling is limited, connecting with our cultural heritage is much more difficult. Within this framework, Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) are showing their full potential. They offer, indeed, the possibility for many to go on with their working activities as well as to cultivate social relationships. But what about tourism and heritage, which are intrinsically based on physical presence and movement?

² See: <https://www.unwto.org/news/covid-19-statement-zurab-pololikashvili>.

For travellers, ICTs are offering opportunities to plan and prepare for their next trips. As it is suggested by a very well-crafted message by Switzerland Tourism, they can help to “Dream now – travel later”. Moreover, this situation of lock-down might help many of us to reflect on the importance of travel, and suggest more sustainable, responsible, and slow travel practices.

For heritage and tourism professionals, ICTs are providing the possibility to valuably spend their time in training and educational activities, in preparation of the new post-crisis challenges. Academia is playing a key role in this direction and several initiatives have been launched, among which we can mention Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), eLearning programs about tourism destinations, educational games, research and publications³. Furthermore, museums and cultural institutions are adjusting their way of working, for instance offering their exhibitions online or opening their archives virtually.

These “Precedings” emphasize the role of ICTs by presenting in its opening section those papers that deal with the use of ITCs for tourism at heritage sites.

Being limited in traveling and having to slow down our usually fast pace, many of us are probably (re)discovering their local tangible and intangible heritage and appreciating its uniqueness and value. If we think about the Holy Week Processions of Mendrisio, the fact that they could not take place raised a nostalgia in the local community, and this might have reinforced people’s sense of belonging and attachment to their traditions. This situation fosters a sort of “slow tourism” in the neighbourhood and a virtual closeness to the people with whom one cannot enjoy the usual festivities or activities, but with whom one shares a common heritage and a common identity. Following these considerations, the second section of these “Precedings” is dedicated to slow tourism and intangible heritage.

The third section comprises papers that tackle the issue of sustainability of tourism at heritage sites, might it be from an economic, social or environmental perspective. The current situation induces us to wonder if the challenges that several heritage sites were facing before the pandemic

³ For instance, USI’s UNESCO Chair in ICT to develop and promote sustainable tourism in World Heritage Sites has launched an ad-hoc initiative, re-opening several online learning resources: <http://www.unescochair.usi.ch/elearning-for-tourism-in-the-time-of-coronavirus>.

will still be existing in the future and which new challenges will arise. Among the ‘old’ challenges are over-tourism, prevention of unintentional damages provoked by distracted tourists, exploitation of natural resources, inaccessibility of sites because of structural or economic boundaries. In the near future, even though traveling with tourism purposes will very likely be allowed again, it is possible that people will have less resources to spend or that they will be afraid to move outside their ‘comfort zone’.

In the fourth section, papers dealing with heritage conservation and promotion are presented. The underlying question, here, is how to improve structural features of built heritage, how to preserve and present intangible heritage, and how to develop conservation plans, so to allow for better visitors’ experiences. In the pandemic framework, the hospitality sector should focus on individual visitors rather than mass-marketing people, caring for their health security while trying to give them a valuable experience.

+++

It has been great to organize everything. Challenging and painful to have to stop. Exciting to know that we are still travelling together, and thanks to these “Precedings” we can continue our collaboration towards a better understanding of Living Heritage and Sustainable Tourism. We would be pleased to keep you informed about future HTHIC editions on www.heritagetourismhospitality.org.

Even far away, let’s stay Unite for Heritage!

Lorenzo Cantoni, Silvia De Ascaniis & Karin Elgin-Nijhuis

(Chairs)

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10. SimilarWeb. <https://www.similarweb.com/website/instagram.com?competitors=tripadvisor.com>, last accessed 2019/03/28.
11. myswissalps. <https://myswissalps.ch>, last accessed 2019/03/22.
12. Sormaz A., Ruoss E. (2019). Social Media Analysis of the Destinations of UNESCO World Heritage Site Swiss Alps Jungfrau-Aletsch. UNESCO Chair in ICT to develop and promote sustainable tourism in World Heritage Sites, Lugano. Internal report.
1. Instagram. <https://www.instagram.com/>, last accessed 2019/03/22.
13. Oxford Dictionary. https://www.lexico.com/en/definition/social_media, last accessed 2019/04/01.
14. TripAdvisor. <https://www.tripadvisor.com>, last accessed 2019/04/04.
15. Ruoss E., Alfarè L. (2013). Challenging Hit and Run Tourism in Cultural Heritage Sites. In L. Marchegiani (ed) *Proceedings of the International Conference on Sustainable Cultural Heritage Management: Societies, Institutions and networks*. ARACNE editrice, Rome, pp. 525-535.
16. Jovanovic V., Njegus A. (2008). The Application of GIS and its components in Tourism. *Yugoslav Journal of Operations Research*: 261-272. DOI: 10.2298/YUJOR0802261J.
17. Think with Google. <https://www.thinkwithgoogle.com/consumer-insights/mobile-influence-travel-decision-making-explore-moments/>, last accessed 2019/04/10.
18. Dolnicar, S. (2008). Market Segmentation in Tourism. In A. Woodside and D. Martin (eds), *Tourism Management: Analysis, Behaviour and Strategy*. CAB International, Cambridge, pp. 129-150.
19. Zagato, L. (2015). The Notion of “Heritage Community” in the Council of Europe’s Faro Convention: Its Impact on the European Legal Framework. In N. Adell, R. F. Bendix, C. Bortolotto and M. Tauschek, *Between Imagined Communities of Practice: Participation, Territory and the Making of Heritage*. Göttingen University Press, Göttingen, pp. 141-168.

The conservation and restoration of heritage as an improvement in the competitiveness of tourist destinations through the vision of tourists. Case study of the Monumental Complex of the Alhambra and the Generalife

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Abstract

The assets that constitute the cultural heritage have the capacity to contribute to the socio-economic development of the territories. Conservation efforts ensure that heritage becomes a resource of such development. The possibilities offered by technology have changed the way information is produced and consumed by the actors involved in tourism. This work tries to identify the effect of heritage conservation on the perception that tourists have of a tourist destination. For this, and through an exploratory qualitative investigation, an analysis of frequencies, semantic network and contents has been carried out based on the comments of tourists on travel blogs and TripAdvisor. The results show that after a restoration process the perception of tourists, expressed in their comments towards the destination, improves considerably.

Keywords: Destination Marketing; Cultural Heritage; Conservation-restoration; Alhambra; social media, Tripadvisor.

1 Introduction

Cultural heritage is currently one of the key factors in strategic activities carried out for the development of territories, as it is an undeniable engine of economic growth, wealth creation and employment (Bowitz and Ibenholt, 2008; Greffe, 2004; Tuan and Navrud, 2008; Wright and Eppink, 2016); for being an identity factor and for its contribution to dialogue and social cohesion (Pasikowska-Schnass, 2018). In this context, the preservation, management and improvement of cultural heritage is more than ever at the center of international debates (Carbone, 2016).

The management of cultural heritage can now be described as a "global practice" guided by a series of internationally recognized codes and letters of conduct that are systematically applied "to maintain the cultural

values of cultural heritage assets for the enjoyment of present generations and future "(Guttentag, 2010; McKercher and du Cross, 2002, p. 43). Numerous studies also coincide in highlighting that it is necessary to involve different stakeholders, including tourists, in the management of tourism and the understanding of its value to achieve the sustainability of heritage tourism. (Mohammad et al., 2016; Vidal et al., 2018; Caust and Vecco, 2017; Poria et al., 2014; Rasoolimanesh et al., 2017; Remoaldo et al. 2014; Robinson, 2015; Saipradist and Staiff, 2008).

In this way, culture and cultural heritage become vital in the process of developing tourist destinations, their attractiveness and their competitiveness (Malek and Costa, 2014; McKercher and du Cross, 2002; Little et al., 2018).

According to Carbone (2016), empirical evidence and theoretical knowledge demonstrate the need to subject the cultural resource to a process of improvement that makes it attractive, accessible and intelligible to the public. In the development of the tourist destination, the appearance of new destinations makes it necessary to strengthen the ability to attract tourists through a high level of competitiveness, which is achieved by the ability of the destination to provide a satisfactory experience to the visitor that motivates him/her to return (and recommend) the visited destination (Alegre and Garau, 2010).

Technological advances have fundamentally changed the way in which actors involved in tourism produce and consume information. Tourists can access different sources of information, and they can generate their own content and share their views and experiences (Alaei, Becken & Stantic, 2019). Travelers have access to online platforms to provide comments and make recommendations for other travelers (Neidhardt, Rümmele and Werthner 2017; Ye, Zhang and Law 2009). As a result, new Internet technologies have empowered people who previously had no voice (Hepburn, 2007). Consumer reviews and social media posts often reflect happiness, frustration, disappointment, delight and other feelings (O'Leary 2011). The analysis and monitoring of these social reviews offer the possibility of knowing the level of immersion within the tourist experiences (Jung et al., 2016) and can be considered profitable methods for the managers of the tourist destinations to

evaluate the quality of their service and improve the overall experiences of travelers (Alaei et al., 2019; Pan, MacLaurin & Crotts, 2007). e, through the analysis of the content of the information collected at

different time points, to determine the incidence that an intervention of restoration of cultural heritage of a tourist destination can cause both in the agents involved in contributing to the preservation of heritage and in the tourists who visit it, focusing on the case of the Monumental Complex of the Alhambra and Generalife.

2 Field of study

The Monumental Complex of the Alhambra and the Generalife has been chosen as a reference tourist destination for this study. It is a Monumental Complex created over more than six hundred years by cultures as diverse as the Muslim, the Renaissance or the Romantic.

Fig. 1. general view of the courtyard of the lions today (authors' image) and lion head nº 7 detail (before and after its restoration). Patronato de la Alhambra y Generalife (2014)

The Monumental Complex of the Alhambra and the Generalife (CMAG) has been included in the World Heritage list since 1984. Since then its importance as a pole of international tourist attraction has not stopped growing. In 2018 it registered 2,724,566 visitors (Ministry of Culture and Historical Heritage, 2018), being one of the most visited monuments in Spain. These figures place it as one of the most attractive tourist sites in Europe. Its economic impact in Granada and the Andalusian Autonomous Community was evident in the study carried out in 2010 (Suriñach and Murillo, 2013).

The area of study of the complex is currently made up of four areas: The Palaces, the Alcazaba, the city or Medina and the Generalife gardens, all in a natural environment. In relation to the interventions carried out and the implication that these imply on the different interested agents as well as the one that can cause in the attraction of tourists, the present study

focuses on knowing the incidence of the intervention carried out in the Palace of the Lions. Its origin dates back to the year 2004, with the transfer of the first lion for restoration and being carried out completely, (Fountain and the other 11 lions), from 2007 to July 2012.

It is precisely these temporary references (pre and post restoration), which will allow to identify if the conservation and restoration of cultural heritage are key in the perception that visitors have of it, and how its realization can contribute to preserving cultural and architectural heritage.

3 Methodology

The methodology used to carry out this study has been qualitatively exploratory. This qualitative methodology allows to obtain a deep knowledge about the opinions, perceptions and attitudes of the individuals about the lived experiences, in relation to their visits to the Alhambra. Firstly, an exploratory investigation was carried out to collect the comments of visitors on travel blogs and on TripAdvisor. Subsequently, the text contained in these comments were analyzed by various research methods: frequency analysis, semantic network analysis and content analysis.

3.1 Data collection

In our study, the sources of information that have been used for the location and extraction of content have been travel blogs (viajered.com, travelers.com, diariodelviajero.com), and the TripAdvisor. Data collection was done at two different points in time: June 2012 (publications made from January 2008 to June 2012) and May 2014 (publications from July 2012 to May 2014). Table 1 shows the number of comments based on the period analyzed (excluding Tripadvisor, of which more data is provided).

Table 1. Data collection summary

	Total Comments	Comments analyzed
January 2008 – June 2012	248	215
June 2012 – May 2014	260	239

For the period until June 2012, out of all the posts analyzed, only 215 contained relevant information for our study, compared to the 239 post of the period from June 2012 to May 2014.

Regarding the information collected from TripAdvisor, it has been considered interesting to carry out a double analysis: on the one hand, the one related to the comments on the Monumental Complex and, on the other, the one related to the assessment given by the visitors and the classification that derives from it. At the time of the first collection of information (June 2012), on TripAdvisor there were 1,759 opinions on the Alhambra and 384 on the Generalife (see table 2). Regarding the Alhambra, most of the comments, 1345, 77%, described the destination as "excellent"; at a great distance, 297 opinions, 17%, considered it "very good"; 77 opinions, 4%, as "normal"; 19 opinions, 1%, as "bad" and 21, 1% as "bad". Regarding the Generalife, 260 opinions, 68%, described it as "excellent"; 100 opinions, 26%, as "very good"; 22 opinions, 6%, as "normal"; "Bad" only 2 opinions, 0% and none rated it as "lousy". In May 2014 the number of opinions on the Alhambra had risen to 6,811 and the Generalife until 1,665. Of these opinions, in the case of the Alhambra, 5,429, 80% described it as "excellent"; 991, 14% as "very good", 252, 4%, opinions considered it "normal"; 65, 1%, valued it as "bad" and 74, 1%, "bad". In the case of the Generalife, 1,172 opinions, 70%, described it as "excellent"; 390, 24%, as "very good"; 89, 5%, as "normal"; 12, 1%, as "bad" and 2 valued it as "bad".

Table 2. Reviews on the Alhambra and the Generalife on Tripadvisor by classification

Classification	June 2012		May 2014	
	Nº comments of Alhambra	Nº comments of Generalife	Nº comments of Alhambra	Nº comments of Generalife
Excellent	1345	260	5.429	1.172
Very good	297	100	991	390
Average	77	22	252	89
Poor	19	2	65	12
Terrible	21	0	74	2

Source: Authors, adapted from TripAdvisor.

The above data show a 287% growth in the number of comments from May 2014 to June 2012. Table 3 shows how comments rated as

“excellent” have grown by 304%, up 4 percentage points from the overall total of comments from the previous period analyzed, and those valued as “very good” have been reduced by 2 percentage points. The rest of the valuations have remained practically constant in their distribution over the overall total of comments, but with a lower growth than the total comments. In the case of Generalife, the growth in the number of comments in the period was 334%. Comments whose rating is “excellent” have a higher than average growth, but the highest growth is observed for bad comments, which had risen by 500%; although in absolute value terms they are very low.

Table 3. Comparative 2014-2012 of the comments on TripAdvisor Alhambra and Generalife by typology

	Alhambra			Generalife		
	2012	2014	Evol.	2012	2014	Evol.
Excellent	76%	80%	304%	67,7%	70,4%	351%
Very good	17%	15%	234%	26,0%	23,4%	290%
Average	4%	4%	227%	5,7%	5,3%	305%
Poor	1%	1%	242%	0,5%	0,7%	500%
Terrible	1%	1%	252%	0,0%	0,1%	

Source: Authors.

3.2 Data Analysis

Once the comments were selected and registered, the next step was to proceed with a detailed analysis of their content. In order to facilitate the processing of the information and the analysis of the data, the summary and classification of the text was carried out together with the natural language processing (NLP) according to the methodology and technology used by other researchers (Pan, MacLaurin and Crotts, 2007; Stringam and Gerdes 2010).

In order to carry out the frequency analysis based on the full text of all valid comments, TextAnalyst was used. For this, the texts were coded considering the characteristics of the tourist destinations, according to the aspects of the tourism model by Cooper et al. (2005) and on the other using the positive or negative orientation of the sentences.

For the codification related to the positive or negative orientation of the sentences, each of the positive or negative aspects of the travel experiences (from the point of view of the visitors at the destination) was

evaluated and categorized, in order to understand the weaknesses and strengths of the Alhambra as a destination.

The semantic network analysis or network representation scheme is a form of linguistic knowledge representation in which concepts and their interrelations are represented by a graph (Newman, Barabási, & Watts, 2006). Therefore, this analysis provides a useful framework for the construction and analysis of content and impressions on the destination, chosen in the study (i.e. the Alhambra in Granada). The most frequently used keywords and phrases are used to construct the semantic network diagram from the CAQDAS Nudist Vivo version 10 software.

Finally, to perform the content analysis of the data collected, the CAQDAS Nudist Vivo version 10 software has been used. Nudist Vivo version 10 has allowed for a more detailed analysis. This tool allows the creation of a category tree (concept map) to illustrate the relationships between the different categories.

The final coding scheme is completed with two dimensions: one formed by the different aspects of the model of Cooper et al. (2005) and a second one based on the evaluation carried out on each of the positive or negative aspects in order to understand the weaknesses and strengths of the Alhambra as a destination. The neutral descriptions of the trip are very few and have been ignored, since the objective of the content analysis is to evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of the Alhambra as a tourist destination.

4 Results

4.1 Frequency analysis

From the frequency analysis performed with TextAnalyst, table 4 shows the most frequently used words in the comments.

In this analysis, several groups of keywords can be extracted by identifying the type of travel experience. The Alhambra and Granada are the most prominent groups, due to the number of visits the Alhambra has per year and the great tourist attraction of the city. Other key aspects in this large cluster are the experiences of tourists in hotels and restaurants, in addition to prices and souvenir shops (being identified as a very important aspect for tourists).

The second large cluster is the set of places that you can visit in the Alhambra along with the experiences of tourists. The great importance of the Palaces is highlighted, specifically the restoration of the Fountain of the Lions, which is considered by some tourists as being the axis that has marked a “before” and “after” in the Alhambra. In addition, one should not forget the theme of tickets and queues, which have to support for their access, the beauty of the Generalife and the splendid Courtyards.

The third cluster is specifically associated with the area in which the Alhambra is located, Granada. This cluster includes the good weather of the city, the friendliness of the people, the number of neighborhoods and views around the Alhambra that can be visited, etc.

4.3 Content Analysis

Regarding the established categories (the comments analyzed were: 273 positive and 82 negative sentences), the results have shown that the main attractions of the Alhambra have positive opinions of tourists about the Monumental Complex in general, followed by opinions on the courtyards, gardens, fountains and the good work of the audio guides and guides.

It can be highlighted that tourists hold positive opinion about the process of conservation and restoration of the monument, especially the Patio de los Leones, the management of ticket collection and the city of Granada itself (especially in some neighborhoods such as El Albaicín).

Fig. 3. Number of positive and negative sentences in the comments analyzed (May 2014)

Finally, the codification of categories and number of positive and negative sentences for each category has been analyzed based on the data selected in the period prior to July 2012. It has been observed, when analyzing some of the main categories, that the results showed interest in the city of Granada in general, and as main attractions of the Alhambra, the Generalife, the Palaces and the Courtyards.

Considering the two periods analyzed, it was observed as a relevant result the fact that in the post-restoration period the total number of positive sentences was much higher than those of the previous period (77% vs. 49%); also for the negative sentences a notable decrease was observed going from 51% in the previous period to 23% in the post-restoration period.

In this sense, the category "construction works" that had 100% of the negative sentences in the first period assumed, in the second period it disappears coinciding with the restoration of the Fountain of the Lions, appearing in its place the category "Conservation and restoration", with 100% positive sentences.

5 Conclusion and Management Implications

The managers of tourist destinations need to know and control the attitudes, opinions and satisfaction levels of visitors with the tourism products and services offered in order to strengthen relationships with potential consumers and improve the provision of such services. For this, it is necessary to know and analyze the characteristics of the tourist demand as well as to be able to identify the weaknesses and strengths of these destinations and study the evolution of these aspects related to the interaction of the visitors with the destination over time. In this way, it will be possible to verify the change of these attitudes and opinions based on the implementation of actions that reinforce strengths and minimize weaknesses.

Consumer reviews and their publications on social networks and on platforms such as TripAdvisor reflect happiness, frustration, disappointment, delight and other feelings in line with O'Leary (2011). To take advantage of these large volumes of "subjective" information, which nonetheless shows the degree of satisfaction or dissatisfaction of the visitor, is of great value for the development of the tourist destination and it allows to improve the competitiveness of the destination through better management of the tourism in line with Choi, Lehto, and Morrison 2007; Ye et al., (2009).

From the data obtained, it is important to highlight how the completion of the restoration process of the Fountain and Patio de los Leones produces an important change in the perception of tourists. These are clear results, which reinforce the notion that conservation and preservation of heritage leads to high levels of satisfaction in line with Alazaizeh et al., (2016).

The managers of the tourist destinations from the information provided by the analysis of the content of the comments should carefully assess the deficiencies and weaknesses detected in order to establish improvement mechanisms, which would minimize the possible negative impact that these comments can cause to the destination. In short, they must establish an action plan. This plan must solve the possible real problems that exist behind these comments that may make the visit experience not as satisfactory as the visitor expects, and also it must communicate the measures adopted, establishment of an effective communication plan and, in some cases pedagogical one, that allows changing the negative perception that the visitors of the destination have.

Thus, both cultural heritage managers and tourist destinations must establish mechanisms to monitor, amplify listening and improve control of what is said about the cultural resource and tourist attraction and its online reputation. They must also expand the communication channels that allow it to maintain a constant relationship with its public and society, so as to improve the ways of promoting the knowledge of its cultural heritage, the services it provides and its involvement in the processes of cultural and socioeconomic development of the city.

Greater demand for cultural experiences and the mobilization of cultural heritage to attract tourists (Bowitz & Ibenholt, 2009) has made cultural heritage one of the most powerful competitive factors for tourist destinations. The management of cultural heritage as a tourist attraction assumes, therefore, a strategic importance for destinations. In this sense, this study shows that the comments, which were included in travel blogs and virtual communities by tourists and travellers, who are continuously sharing their experiences with the visit to cultural heritage are a source of useful information for the managers of the tourist destinations, especially when it comes to knowing the opinion of the tourists in order to detect the strengths and weaknesses.

6 References

1. Alaei, A. R., Becken, S., & Stantic, B. (2019). Sentiment analysis in tourism: capitalizing on big data. *Journal of Travel Research*, 58(2), 175-191.
2. Alazaizeh, M.M., Hallo, J.C., Backman, S., Norman, W., Vogel, M. (2016). "Value orientations and heritage tourism management at Petra Archaeological Park, Jordan". *Tourism Management* 57: 149-158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2016.05.008>
3. Alegre, J., & Garau, J. (2010). Tourist satisfaction and dissatisfaction. *Annals of tourism research*, 37(1), 52-73.
4. Bowitz, E. & Ibenholt, K. (2008). Economic impacts of cultural heritage. Research and perspectives. *Journal of Cultural Heritage*, 10(1), 1-8.
5. Carbone, F. (2016) An insight into cultural heritage management of tourism destinations. *European of Journal Tourism Research*, 14, 75–91.
6. Caust, J., Vecco, M. (2017) "Is UNESCO World Heritage recognition a blessing or burden? Evidence from developing Asian countries". *Journal of Cultural Heritage*, 27: 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2017.02.004>
7. Choi, S., X. Y. Lehto, and A. M. Morrison. 2007. "Destination Image Representation on the Web: Content Analysis of Macao Travel Related Websites." *Tourism Management* 28 (1): 118-129.
8. Consejería de Cultura y Patrimonio Histórico. Junta de Andalucía. https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/cultura/estadisticas_cultura/operaciones/consulta/anual/14966?CodOper=b3_893&codConsulta=14966
9. Cooper, C., Fletcher, J., Gilbert, D., Fyall, A., & Wanhill, S. (2005). *Tourism: Principles and practice*. Pearson education.

10. Greffe, X. (2004). Is heritage an asset or a liability? *Journal of Cultural Heritage*, 5(3), 301-309.
11. Guttentag, D. A. (2010). Virtual reality: Applications and implications for tourism. *Tourism Management*, 31(5), 637–651. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2016.05.008>
12. Hepburn, C. 2007. Web 2.0 for the Tourism and Travel Industry: A White Paper. ICT-Technical Reports, Laboratory for Intelligent Systems
13. Jung, T. H., Dieck, M. C., Lee, H., & Chung, N. (2016). Effects of virtual reality and augmented reality on visitor experiences in museum. In A. Inversini, & R. Schegg (Eds.). *Information and communication technologies in tourism* (pp. 621–635). Cham, Switzerland: Springer.
14. Little, C., Patterson, D., Moyle, B., & Bec, A. (2018). Every footprint tells a story: 3D scanning of heritage artefacts as an interactive experience. Paper presented at the Australasian computer science week multiconference, Victoria, Australia 31 January- 3 February.
15. Malek, A., & Costa, C. (2015). Integrating communities into tourism planning through social innovation. *Tourism Planning & Development*, 12(3), 281-299.
16. McKercher, B., & Du Cros, H. (2002). *Cultural tourism: The partnership between tourism and cultural heritage management*. New York: Haworth Hospitality Press.
17. Neidhardt, J., Rümmele, N., & Werthner, H. (2017). Predicting happiness: user interactions and sentiment analysis in an online travel forum. *Information Technology & Tourism*, 17(1), 101-119.
18. Newman, M. E., Barabási, A. L. E., & Watts, D. J. (2006). *The structure and dynamics of networks*. Princeton university press.
19. O’Leary, D. 2011. “The Use of Social Media in the Supply Chain: Survey and Extensions.” *Intelligent Systems in Accounting, Finance and Management* 18 (2-3): 121-44.
20. Pan, B., T. MacLaurin, and J. C. Crotts. 2007. “Travel Blogs and the Implications for Destination Marketing.” *Journal of Travel Research* 46 (1): 35-45.
21. Patronato de la Alhambra y Generalife (2014). *Restoration of The Courtyard of the Lions* p. 42. Ed. Patronato de la Alhambra y Generalife.
22. Pasikowska-Schnass, M. *Cultural Heritage in EU Policies*; European Union, European Parliamentary Research Service: Brussels, Belgium, 2018. Available online: [http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2018/621876/EPRS_BRI\(2018\)621876_EN.pdf](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2018/621876/EPRS_BRI(2018)621876_EN.pdf) (accessed on 3 September 2019).
23. Pekar, V., & Ou, S. (2008). Discovery of subjective evaluations of product features in hotel reviews. *Journal of Vacation Marketing*, 14(2), 145-155.
24. Poria, Y., Stanislav Ivanov, S.; Webster, C. (2014) “Attitudes and willingness to donate towards heritage restoration: an exploratory study about Bulgarian socialist monuments”. *Journal of Heritage Tourism*, 9(1): 68-74, DOI: 10.1080/1743873X.2013.778266
25. Rasoolimanesh, S.M., Jaafar, M., Ahmad A.G., Barghi, R. (2017). “Community participation in World Heritage Site conservation and tourism development”. *Tourism Management* 58: 142-153
26. Remoaldo, P. C., Ribeiro, J.C., Vareiro, L., Santos, J.F. (2014). “Tourists’ perceptions of world heritage destinations: The case of Guimaraes (Portugal)”. *Tourism and Hospitality Research*, 14(4) 206–218. DOI: 10.1177/1467358414541457
27. Robinson, K., 2015. World heritage listed sites – Does it attract tourists? A study of factors influencing Norwegian tourist’s intention to visit Unesco’s world heritage listed sites. Master Thesis. BE309E International Business and Marketing. University of Nordland.